

MADRAS

D5.9 Visual Corporative Image

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2019 GA No. 862492
Project title	Advanced Materials and Processing in Organic Electronics (MADRAS)
Duration of the project	April 2020 - April 2023 (36 months)
WP/Task:	WP5 - 5.7
Document due Date:	30/06/2020
Actual date of delivery	30/06/2020
Leader of this deliverable	EURECAT
Dissemination level	Public
Document status	Submitted

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	28/05/2020	Míriam Vendrell	1 st Draft
0.2	02/06/2020	Marina Presas	1 st Draft revision
0.3	10/06/2020	Laura López	Revision
0.4	25/06/2020	Partners revision	Revision
1.0	29/06/2020	Rosa Araujo	Final revision

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MADRAS project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862492 (Art. 29.4)

Executive summary

This deliverable explains how Eurecat, as the leader of Communication and Dissemination tasks, has developed MADRAS's **Visual Corporative Image (VCI)**. This document includes the **project's logo**, **Word templates for project activities**, a **Power Point template for presentations** and a **visual identity standards guidebook** defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to MADRAS, such as logos, colours, fonts and graphic elements.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EUT</i>	<i>Eurecat</i>
<i>IMPE</i>	<i>In Mould Electronics</i>
<i>OLAE</i>	<i>Organic and Large Area Electronics</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporative Image</i>

Introduction

MADRAS is a 3-year research project aiming to demonstrate a **materials-driven improvement of OLAE devices, developing a high-speed manufacturing methodology in a scalable competitive process, which is In Mould Electronics (IME).**

The project also addresses the need for innovative and industrial manufacturing processes for the development of robust series of plastronics products. Building on an already established technology as plastic injection will facilitate a faster up taking.

In addition, MADRAS project proposes two products for persons' authentication market and smart manufacturing that will show a step forward towards digitisation and Internet of Things for its contribution to the sustainable deployment of smart products for consumer use.

Eurecat is the partner leader of **Task 5.7 Communication Activities**, which has the objective to create and provide all the communication materials needed for conveying the project to a broad group of users. This task includes the design of the **Corporate Visual Image** created by EUT during M1 and M2. This document presents the materials designed including a logo, a presentation template, word documents templates and a visual identity manual to be implemented in all communication and dissemination project activities.

Project's Visual Corporative Image

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing MADRAS official Visual Corporative Image (VCI), aimed at properly aligning all communication materials across all the tasks of the project.

The Visual Corporative Image is essential to create and establish MADRAS' identity, as well as to give a coherent and consistent image of the project. **It is important to use the elements established in the VCI manual properly and only employ the authorized documents templates in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand and do it consistently.**

The following sections describe the different materials and elements designed, including the project's logo, templates, colours, fonts and graphic elements to be used and implemented in all communication and dissemination actions by all project's partners.

1. MADRAS Logo

The logo is the main brand element of the visual identity of MADRAS and has the objective to represent the different concepts surrounding the project. The project's logo refers to the OLAE materials in which functional printing can be used. More specifically, **this logo aims to represent that the novelty of the project relies in using a new transparent semiconductor and conductive cellulose as a printed electronics substrate.**

As pictured in Figure 1, MADRAS's logo shape symbolizes an electronic circuit printed on a leaf and includes the two main colours of the project and the acronym with the special font used for some project materials and established in the project's visual identity manual.

Figure 1: MADRAS full colour logo

Figure 2: MADRAS black and white logo

The elements of the logo, which are the shape of a leaf and the project's acronym, cannot be used separately in any case. Moreover, different versions of the logo have been created to be used in different supports and depending on the background colour.

When using a background with an image or with a corporative colour, the logo must be placed inside a white box. For the design of project promotional materials as the rollup or flyers, which should include an image background, the MADRAS's logo with the white box will also be used.

Figure 3: MADRAS logo inside the white box

Figure 4: Logo adaptation on a green corporate colour background

Figure 5: Logo adaptation on a background with an image

All the versions and uses of the logo are included in the MADRAS's Visual Corporate Identity manual shared with all partners and attached in the annexes of this deliverable.

2. Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual

A visual identity and standards guidebook have been produced and distributed among partners to ensure that project's branding is not compromised, and all partners use the elements properly in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand.

The visual identity manual defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to MADRAS including logos, colours, fonts, stationery and graphic resources. In addition, it sets a design layout for project promotional materials to be developed in the following months. Partners should treat the guidebook as a source of the materials and instructions and as a basis for further development of project materials.

The sections hereinafter include and describe some parts of the manual.

2.1 Corporate colours

This section presents the MADRAS colours palette that must be used in all project materials, such as the website, social media and other promotional and graphic resources.

According to the palette designed, the main colour of MADRAS project is green (Pantone: 3275C) while black (Pantone: Black 6C) and lemon green (Pantone: 381C) will be the complementary colours of the project.

Figure 6: MADRAS colours palette

2.2 Fonts

The Visual Corporate Image manual establishes three types of fonts to be used for project documents and materials.

“**RIGHTEOUS**”, which can be used only in capital letters, will be the **special font used for titles of promotional and advertising materials**. This type of font and its different versions are free, and partners can download it in Google Fonts page. As the manual determines, the text font for promotional and communication items will be “Barlow Semi Condensed”.

Download the “RIGHTEOUS” font [here](#)

On the other hand, “**Trebuchet MS**” is the **main font established for deliverables and internal documents** because it is a standard Microsoft Office included in Word and Power Point documents, among others. The use of this font will be explained in more detail in following sections.

Fonts

Special Font
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Righteous>

Text Font
for promotional items
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Barlow+Semi+Condensed>

RIGHTEOUS

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

USE ONLY CAPITAL CHARACTERS!

<p>Barlow Semi Condensed Light</p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Barlow Semi Condensed Light Italic</i></p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>
<p>Barlow Semi Condensed Regular</p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Barlow Semi Condensed Italic</i></p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>
<p>Barlow Semi Condensed Semibold</p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Barlow Semi Condensed Semibold Italic</i></p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>

Figure 7: MADRAS fonts for promotional materials

Fonts

Text Font
for deliverables and internal documents
only

<p>Trebuchet MS regular</p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Trebuchet MS italic</i></p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>
<p>Trebuchet MS bold</p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>	<p><i>Trebuchet MS bold italic</i></p> <p>abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ 0123456789</p>

Figure 8: MADRAS fonts for deliverables and internal documents

2.3 Stationery

The MADRAS Visual Corporate Identity manual also includes different elements designed for stationery materials, such as letters, envelopes, business cards, the image of the project for digital supports and applications and other internal and external documents, that partners could use when it is needed.

Figure 9: MADRAS stationery

2.4 Graphic resources

This section includes the graphic items which can be used for the design of promotional materials, external and internal project presentations or other documents. **These elements have been broadly used for the design of project Word and Power Point templates, as well as headers for the project's Twitter account.**

Figure 10: Graphic resources for designing project's materials

2.5 Promotional and advertising materials layout

Different promotional and marketing materials templates have been produced to be used for the design of flyers, rollups, totems and social media headers.

The Visual Corporate Image manual also includes different proposals of design for project's promotional and marketing materials, such as the rollup and flyer which will be created at M6 of the project, according to the communication and dissemination actions calendar.

Some screenshots are included below:

Figure 11: Flyer template

Figure 12: Rollup templates

2.6 Twitter Header

The VCI manual also includes a Twitter header template which has been already used and integrated in the project's account.

Figure 13: Twitter header templates

Figure 14: MADRAS Twitter page with the header designed

3. Templates

Communication Leader Eurecat has prepared different templates, which have been shared with all partners. A power point template has been produced for internal and external presentations, as well as three different Word documents: one for deliverables, one for meetings' agenda and other purposes and another one to be used for minutes.

These template materials will be used throughout all the project's execution to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

3.1 Template for deliverables

A Word document template has been created and shared with partners to be used for all project's deliverables.

This template establishes the use of a page header with the project's logo and the funding body's logo and a footer with some information about the document and a graphic element created for project materials.

Other aspects included in the deliverable template are specified here:

- **Normal Text** is Trebuchet MS 10pt, single line spacing and justified.
- **Titles Text** is Trebuchet MS, bold and in main project corporate colour (Pantone: 3275C).
- Each section has to start at a new page.

- **Footnote:** notes placed at the bottom of a page of a book that comments on or cites a reference for a designated part of the text have to be set apart from the text by a 5 cm long line.
- If using an **excerpt from a book or a scientific article** it is proper to place it in indentation using style as follows:

This paragraph report directly another's words. As you can see there is indentation of 1,2cm from left and right while there are spaces of 8pt. from the previous and from the next paragraph. The font is Times New Roman, 11pt.

- Styles for use unordered and unordered lists.

*See an example of an unordered list:

- In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.
 - In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.
 - In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.
 - In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.
 - In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.

*See an example of an ordered list:

1. In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.
 - i. In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.
 - ii. In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.
 - a. In in massa rutrum, porta sapien vel, suscipit lectus.

Figure 15: View of some pages of the project's deliverable template

3.2 Template for agenda

The template designed for the agenda presents a header page with the MADRAS and funding body’s logos and a footer with some information and a graphic element that symbolises the “M” of the project acronym.

The font used for title in agenda’s document are **Trebuchet MS 16pt, bold** and in main project corporate colour (Pantone: 3275C) and for the normal text is also **Trebuchet MS 10pt, single line spacing and justified**.

A screenshot is shown below:

Figure 16: Word template for agenda

3.3 Template for minutes

This template will be used to present the minutes and the list of attendants to an internal project meeting. The document includes a header page with the MADRAS and funding body’s logos and a footer with some information and a graphic element.

For general title of the document it will be used the **Trebuchet MS 16pt, bold** and in main project corporate colour (Pantone: 3275C), for subsections headings the font used are **Trebuchet MS, 14pt** and for normal text also **Trebuchet MS 11pt**.

Some screenshots are included below:

Figure 17: Word template for minutes

3.4 Power Point Presentation Template

A Power Point template has been designed to be used for all project's internal and external presentations.

This document presents a variety of slides with different options to include the text and different visual elements to be used and adapted by all partners when preparing an internal or external project's presentation.

A screenshot of some slides is shown below:

Figure 18: Slides of MADRAS Power Point template

ANNEX

1. MADRAS Visual Corporate Image Manual

MADRAS

A project coordinated by:

eurecat

Visual Identity Standards Guidebook

This visual identity guide defines and outlines how to use identifying elements pertaining to **Madrás** including logos, colors, fonts, stationery, and some marketing and advertising materials.

It is very important to use these elements properly and only employ the authorized document templates in order to convey the properties and goals of the Project as a brand, and do it consistently.

Please treat this guidebook as the source of the materials and instructions on what is and is not permissible, and as basis for further development of the Project's materials.

If changes to the visual standards are needed, updates to this guidebook will be made and distributed. Any questions about this guide and its contents should be directed to:

Marina Presas

Responsible for MADRAS'

Communication and Dissemination Tasks

marina.presas@eurecat.org

Full Color Logo

Version 1

MADRAS

B/W Logo

Positive

MADRAS

B/W Logo

Negative

MADRAS

Use of the logo

MADRAS

Colors

Main Color:

Green:

PRINT
COLORS

PANTONE 3275 C
CMYK: 95 | 0 | 50 | 0

SCREEN
COLORS

RGB: 60 | 230 | 180
WEB: #3CE6B4

Complementary Colors:

Black:

PANTONE BLACK 6 C
CMYK: 90 | 80 | 60 | 100

PRINT
COLORS

RGB: 255 | 255 | 255
WEB: #FFFFFF

SCREEN
COLORS

Lemon Green:

PANTONE 381 C
CMYK: 30 | 0 | 100 | 0

PRINT
COLORS

RGB: 190 | 240 | 50
WEB: #C0EF30

SCREEN
COLORS

Fonts

Special Font
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Righteous>

RIGHTEOUS

ABCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

USE ONLY CAPITAL CHARACTERS!

Text Font
for promotional items
<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Barlow+Semi+Condensed>

Barlow Semi Condensed Light

abcdefghijklmnopqrstu vwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Barlow Semi Condensed Light Italic

*abcdefghijklmnopqrstu vwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789*

Barlow Semi Condensed Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstu vwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Barlow Semi Condensed Italic

*abcdefghijklmnopqrstu vwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789*

Barlow Semi Condensed Semibold

**abcdefghijklmnopqrstu vwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789**

Barlow Semi Condensed Semibold Italic

***abcdefghijklmnopqrstu vwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKL MNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789***

Fonts

Text Font
for deliverables and
internal documents
only

Trebuchet MS regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLONOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Trebuchet MS bold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLONOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

Trebuchet MS italic

*abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLONOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789*

Trebuchet MS bold italic

*abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
ABCDEFGHIJKLONOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789*

Stationery

B
MADRAS

To:
Name and Surname

Dear Name and Surname

Cras ac justo varius, tristique dolor lobortis, tincidunt felis. Nam vitae magna tempus, ullamcorper arcu eget, egestas mi. Mauris vel diam iaculis, pharetra metus nec, luctus mi. Sed elementum semper risus, vitae interdum odio condimentum in. Sed mattis maximus sapien, ut lacinia mi luctus sit amet. Praesent non pulvinar risus. Maecenas ut libero quis arcu mollis lobortis et nec purus. Quisque aliquet erat eget dolor tempor vehicula. Integer accumsan eu est ut tincidunt. Maecenas posuere, ligula sed efficitur viverra, tellus turpis malesuada libero, eu maximus nisl dui at velit. Vivamus et lectus varius, malesuada lorem non, dapibus lorem. Sed at ex consequat, iaculis massa eget, maximus leo. Ut auctor interdum gravida. Integer vel ipsum sit amet quam mollis pulvinar. Orci varius natoque penatibus et magnis dis parturient montes, nascetur ridiculus mus. Aenean sed lectus nec dui faucibus fermentum a id magna.

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Sincerely,

Name and Surname

B
Madras
Street Name 00, 1-4
08080, Barcelona
Catalonia, Spain
T. +34 123 456 789
M. user@madras.com

MADRAS

B **NAME AND SURNAME**
Position in the company

Street Name 00, 1-4
08080, Barcelona
Catalonia, Spain
T. +34 123 456 789
M. user@madras.com

MADRAS

MADRAS

B
MADRAS

MADRAS

AT VERO EOS ET ACCUSAMUS ET IUSTO ODIO DIGNISSIMOS DUCIMUS QUI BLANDITIS PRAESENTIUM.

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NEMO ENIM IPSAM VOLUPTATEM QUIA VOLUPTAS EST.

MADRAS

MADRAS
Street Name 00, 1-4
08080, Barcelona
Catalonia, Spain
T: +34 932 456 789
M: user@madras.com

Neque porro quisquam est, qui dolorem ipsum quia dolor sit amet, consectetur est.

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MADRAS

MADRAS

NEMO ENIM IPSAM VOLUPTATEM QUIA VOLUPTAS EST.

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Twitter Headers

Graphic resources

Graphic items
Design corporative resources

D
D
B
B

MADRAS

MADRAS

D
D
B
B

MADRAS

MADRAS